

Effect of fish oil in Iberian sow diets on fatty acid, oxylipins and immune traits of colostrum and milk, and suckling piglets' growth performance

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 11 June 2024

Revised 13 January 2025

Accepted 14 January 2025

Available online 21 January 2025

Keywords:

Iberian pigs

Lactation

Maternal passive immunity

n-3 long-chain fatty acids

Oxygenated lipid mediators

ABSTRACT

Iberian sow productivity is characterised by a low number of weaned piglets with higher within-litter variation in piglet birth BW compared with conventional breeds. To overcome this, nutritional strategies, such as the dietary addition of n-3 fatty acids (FAs), are being studied to improve sow performance, as well as colostrum and milk composition. In addition, n-3 FAs and their derived oxylipins could also be beneficial for the offspring due to their anti-inflammatory roles. The present study was conducted in an outdoor production system where sows were group-fed during the mating and gestation periods, while feed intake was provided individually during lactation. The study aimed to evaluate the effects of including fish oil rich in eicosapentaenoic and docosahexaenoic acids (EPA and DHA, respectively) in Iberian sow diets on litter size, piglet growth during lactation, and the concentrations of anti-inflammatory molecules in colostrum and milk. Forty sows were randomly assigned to either a control or fish oil diet during pregnancy and lactation. Sow performance and litter traits were monitored until weaning. Colostrum and milk were collected after the birth of the first piglet and at weaning, respectively. Their FA composition, oxylipin profile, and immune indicators were analysed. Despite the piglets from the control group having greater average birth BW than those from the fish oil litters ($P = 0.016$), the fish oil piglets were heavier at weaning ($P < 0.028$). Total n-3 FA concentration was increased in the colostrum and milk of fish oil-fed sows (all $P < 0.001$), mainly due to increases in EPA and DHA concentrations (all $P < 0.001$). In the same way, most of their oxygenated derivatives were also increased in both colostrum and milk ($P \leq 0.045$). The colostrum from fish oil-fed sows also presented higher concentrations of immunoglobulins (Ig) G and A than that from control sows ($P = 0.025$ and $P = 0.026$, respectively). In conclusion, the inclusion of fish oil in sow diets increased the levels of IgG and IgA in colostrum, n-3 FAs and their derived oxylipins in colostrum and milk, and piglet BW at weaning.

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Implications

Iberian sows wean a low number of piglets. Piglet mortality during lactation is also high. An improvement in the quality of colostrum and milk could influence piglet survival and growth. In the present study, the inclusion of fish oil in Iberian sow diets during gestation and lactation increased piglet weight gain during lactation and their BW at weaning. Dietary fish oil also increased the concentrations of n-3 fatty acids and their derived oxylipins in

colostrum and milk, as well as the levels of immunoglobulins G and A in colostrum. This could enhance the immune protection of suckling piglets.

Introduction

The Iberian pig is the most abundant and well-known autochthonous breed in Europe (Bozzi et al., 2020), mainly due to the recognised high-quality of their cured products (Tejerina et al., 2012). However, Iberian pigs exhibit lower production performance than conventional pig breeds since the number of piglets weaned per litter in Iberian sows is considerably lower than in conventional sows, under both intensive and extensive production systems (Duarte et al., 2013) (7.2 piglets in the Iberian breed vs 12.3 piglets in conventional breeds in 2023 according to IRTA,

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2023). As for conventional breeds, piglet mortality during lactation is also an important economic and animal welfare problem in Iberian pigs (Nieto et al., 2019), reaching 12.8% of total live-born piglets (IRTA, 2023). Considering that newborn piglets are highly vulnerable due to their lack of energy stores and immune protection (Le Dividich et al., 2005), an improvement in the quality of colostrum and milk from sows could exert a direct influence on piglet survival and growth. Colostrum is secreted during approximately the first 24 h of life, thus providing the first source of energy and maternal antibodies to the piglets, and afterwards, the composition gradually changes to that of milk, which is notable for its lower protein and higher fat content (Le Dividich et al., 2005). Therefore, developing nutritional strategies to enhance the composition of colostrum and milk is of interest to improve piglet growth and survival during lactation and for more efficient Iberian pig production.

The use of n-3 fatty acids (FAs) in swine nutrition has been studied for several years. Specifically, research has focused mainly on their inclusion in sow diets during gestation and/or lactation to study their effects on milk production and composition, litter characteristics at birth, and piglet vitality and growth (Tanghe and De Smet, 2013; Lauridsen, 2020). In addition, the oxidation products of these n-3 FAs, metabolites known as oxylipins, have also been linked to some anti-inflammatory or inflammation-resolving capacities in other animal species (Calder, 2010). Furthermore, due to their anti-inflammatory properties, their use for the improvement of piglet health has recently gained interest.

Within the project of the current study, the impact of a dietary fish oil source rich in eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA) on performance, litter characteristics, and colostrum and milk composition (in terms of FAs, oxylipins, and immune indicators) has been already assessed in Landrace x Large White conventional sows (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021; Llauradó-Calero, 2023). In those studies, it was observed that piglets weaned from sows fed the n-3 FA-rich diet tended to be heavier than those from sows fed the control diet; however, at the same time, the litter size tended to be 0.7 piglets smaller. Furthermore, EPA, DHA, and their oxygenated derivatives were significantly increased in both colostrum and milk of sows fed the n-3 FA diet, immunoglobulins (Ig) did not differ between dietary treatments, and n-3 FA only resulted in decreased tumour necrosis factor- α (TNF- α) and a trend to decreased interleukin (IL)-10 concentrations in milk. In the present study, we hypothesised that the use of the same fish oil source as in the study by Llauradó-Calero et al. (2021) in the diet of Iberian sows could modify the composition of colostrum and milk and improve suckling piglet growth. However, since the Iberian breed has not been selected for productive traits as intensively as conventional breeds, the use of n-3 FAs as a nutritional strategy in Iberian sows may produce different results. Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the impact of dietary n-3 FAs in Iberian sow diets on suckling piglet growth and colostrum and milk composition (in terms of FAs, oxylipins, and immune indicators). Preliminary results have been published in abstract form (García-Gudiño et al., 2022; Llauradó-Calero et al., 2023).

Material and methods

Animals, housing, and experimental design

The experiment was carried out at the Valdesequera farm (+39° 3' 13.2", -6° 50' 45.2"), belonging to CICYTEX, in the southwest of Spain. The experiment lasted from sow mating until weaning (day 30 of lactation), and spanned different seasons: mating took place in winter (January to March, with temperatures ranging from 4 °C to 20 °C), gestation took place throughout winter and spring (with

temperatures ranging from 5 °C to 31 °C), and farrowing and lactation took place between May and August, spanning spring and summer (with temperatures ranging from 12 °C to 35 °C). This study was conducted using 40 Iberian sows in two consecutive management lots that were 44 days apart (20 sows per lot). Sows were randomly assigned to treatment groups (either control or n-3 long-chain FAs (n-3 LCFA)-rich diet), in a stratified manner according to parity number (3rd to 7th) and BW. Once the randomisation of animals was completed, previous litters were weaned, and mating started three days later. The mating was arranged by housing the sows in large outdoor pens (100 m long x 12 m wide) with the Iberian boars (one boar and 20 females from the two management lots per pen). After removing the boars (45 days after sow inclusion), the sows remained in the same outdoor pens during gestation. Thus, the sows from the two diet groups were housed in two separate large outdoor pens with 50% cement and 50% soil flooring during this period. Due to the characteristics of the outdoor production system, sows were group-fed during the mating and gestation periods. One week before farrowing, sows were moved into individual indoor facilities where environmental conditions were controlled. Illumination was natural daylight through windows, resulting in an average daily light duration of 14–15 h, and the climate control system was maintained at a stable temperature range of 23–26 °C. Sows were placed in pens (2.4 m x 1.5 m) including an individual farrowing crate (1.7 m x 0.6 m). Pens had slatted flooring and a heated floor plate for the piglets, ensuring optimal thermal conditions of 32–34 °C. Sows were fed from individual feeders, and feed intake was recorded individually during lactation. At 15 days of age, piglets also received control or n-3 LCFA creep feeding supplementation from small dish feeders attached to the slatted floor in accordance with the sow's experimental diet. Water was made available to the sows *ad libitum* from nipple drinkers. The amount of feed supplied to sows was restricted to 2 kg/day during gestation and was gradually increased after farrowing until reaching 4 kg/day on the 5th day after farrowing (3 kg/day from day 1 to 3 and 3.5 kg the 4th day after farrowing). During gestation, the compound feed ration was weighed daily for each outdoor pen.

Experimental diets

Sow diets were formulated following FEDNA's specifications for conventional gestating sows (de Blas et al., 2013), and the same diets were used during gestation and lactation. Sows were fed a control diet containing 15 g/kg of animal fat or an n-3 LCFA diet in which animal fat was totally replaced by an equivalent amount (i.e., 21.5 g/kg) of a solid fish oil source (Lipomega[®]; V&S Asociados, Madrid, Spain). The piglets' control creep feed contained 30.7 g/kg of animal fat, which was also entirely replaced by the equivalent amount of solid fish oil (48.6 g/kg) in the corresponding creep feed diet of the n-3 LCFA treatment group. Diets were formulated to be nutritionally equivalent except for the FA composition. The ingredient composition, estimated nutrients, and FA contents are shown in Table 1.

Growth measurements and sample collection

Iberian sows were weighed at the start of the mating period, upon entering the farrowing unit, and at weaning. At the same time points, interscapular and sacral dorsal fat were also measured with an ExaGo ultrasound machine (IMV Technologies, L'Aigle, France), and measurements were taken using Biosoft Toolbox[®] II (Biotronics Inc., IA, USA). Sows' average daily weight gain was calculated from the beginning of mating until entering the farrowing unit (gestation) and from entering the farrowing unit until weaning (lactation). The total number of piglets, live-born, stillborn,

Table 1
Ingredient and nutrient composition of gestating and lactating Iberian sow diets and creep feed (as fed basis).

Item	Gestating and lactating sow diet		Creep feed	
	Control	n-3 LCFA	Control	n-3 LCFA
Ingredient (g/kg)				
Barley	446	438	300	300
Corn	200	200	200	200
Sunflower seed meal	100	100	–	–
Wheat	80.0	80.0	239	221
Sugar-beet pulp	80.0	80.0	–	–
Soybean meal 47%	40.6	42.7	154	154
Dicalcium phosphate	15.4	15.4	5.30	5.30
Lard ¹	15.0	–	30.7	–
Fish oil (Lipomega ^{®2})	–	21.5	–	48.6
L-lysine HCL	1.30	1.30	–	–
L-threonine	0.20	0.20	–	–
Calcium carbonate	13.3	13.3	3.00	8.00
Sodium bicarbonate + Magnesium oxide	4.30	4.30	–	–
Sodium chloride	0.80	0.80	3.00	3.00
Vitamin-Mineral premix ^{3,4}	3.00	3.00	60.0	60.0
Estimated nutrient composition ⁵ (g/kg)				
DM	874	874	833	835
ME (MJ/kg)	12.5	12.7	13.2	13.5
Crude fibre	67.1	66.8	27.9	27.5
Ether extract	35.8	34.3	49.6	49.3
CP	131	131	146	144
Lysine	6.11	6.14	6.64	6.58
Estimated fatty acid composition ⁶ (%)				
C14:0	0.608	0.725	0.462	0.750
C16:0	16.6	16.5	15.5	15.5
C16:1	0.202	0.326	0.293	0.573
C18:0	1.98	1.90	1.98	1.83
C18:1 n-9 <i>cis</i>	16.3	15.9	17.4	16.5
C18:2 n-6 <i>cis</i>	53.9	53.5	49.8	48.7
C18:3 n-3 <i>cis</i>	4.35	4.34	4.45	4.40
C20:4 n-6	0.002	0.023	0.003	0.052
C20:5 n-3	0.002	0.245	0.003	0.553
C22:6 n-3	0.002	0.212	0.003	0.479

Abbreviations: LCFA = long-chain fatty acid; ME = metabolisable energy.

¹ Product of Intexur, S.L. (Higuera la Real, Spain). It contains myristic acid (C14:0) 1.40%, palmitic acid (C16:0) 25.0%, palmitoleic acid (C16:1) 2.80%, stearic acid (C18:0) 12.8%, oleic acid (C18:1 n-9 *cis*) 47.2%, linoleic acid (C18:2 n-6 *cis*) 7.40%, α -linolenic acid (C18:3 n-3 *cis*) 0.50%, arachidonic acid (C20:4 n-6 *cis*) 0.10%, eicosapentaenoic acid (C20:5 n-3 *cis*) <0.10%, and docosahexaenoic acid (C22:6 n-3 *cis*) < 0.10%.

² Product of V&S Asociados (Madrid, Spain). It contains 63.36% of fat and 36.64% of the inert excipient Tixosil[®] silica (Solvay, Brussels, Belgium). Analysed fatty acid composition per gram of fat: 42.2 mg of myristic acid (C14:0), 129.1 mg of palmitic acid (C16:0), 33.0 mg of stearic acid (C18:0), 106.1 mg of oleic acid (C18:1 n-9 *cis*), 26.3 mg of linoleic acid (C18:2 n-6 *cis*), 12.2 mg of α -linolenic acid (C18:3 n-3 *cis*), 7.95 mg of arachidonic acid (C20:4 n-6 *cis*), 89.9 mg of eicosapentaenoic acid (C20:5 n-3 *cis*), and 72.7 mg of docosahexaenoic acid (C22:6 n-3 *cis*).

³ Sow vitamin-mineral premix (Nuscience Ibérica S.A.U., Casarrubios del Monte, Spain) supplying per kilogram of feed: Ca 0.3 mg, digestible P 0.8 mg, vitamin A (3a672a) 12 000 IU, vitamin D₃ (3a671) 2 000 IU, vitamin E (3a700) 49 mg, vitamin K₃ (3a710) 1 mg, vitamin B₁ (3a821) 1 mg, vitamin B₂ (3a825i) 4 mg, calcium D-pantothenate (3a841) 16 mg, vitamin B₆ (3a831) 2 mg, vitamin B₁₂ 0.02 mg, niacinamide (3a315) 25 mg, folic acid (3a316) 2 mg, biotin (3a880) 0.2 mg, choline chloride (3a890) 253 mg, Fe (3b103) (from FeSO₄·H₂O) 90 mg, Cu (3b405) (from CuSO₄·5H₂O) 15 mg, Zn (3b603) (from ZnO) 108 mg, Mn (3b502) (from MnO) 49 mg, I (3b202) (from Ca(IO₃)₂) 1 mg, Se (3b801) (from Na₂SeO₃) 0.3 mg, Sepiolite (E-562) 651 mg, propyl gallate (E-310) 0.2 mg, butylhydroxytoluene (BHT) (E-321) 0.2 mg, 6-ftase EC 3.1.3.26 (4a27) 300 FTU, other additives: Citric acid (E-330).

⁴ Piglet vitamin-mineral premix (Nuscience Ibérica S.A.U., Casarrubios del Monte, Spain) supplying per kilogram of feed: biotin (3a880) 0.2 mg, choline chloride (3a890) 540 mg, Fe (3b103) (from FeSO₄·H₂O) 100.5 mg, Fe (3b108) (from hydrated glycine iron chelate) 10 mg, Cu (3b405) (from CuSO₄·5H₂O) 135.5 mg, Zn (3b603) (from ZnO) 110 mg, Mn (3b502) (from MnO) 42.7 mg, I (3b202) (from Ca(IO₃)₂) 2.3 mg, Se (3b801) (from Na₂SeO₃) 0.1 mg, Sepiolite (E-562) 1 063.6 mg, propyl gallate (E-310) 6.9 mg, butylhydroxyanisole (BHA) (E-320) 1.2 mg, butylhydroxytoluene (BHT) (E-321) 12.2 mg, fumaric acid (1a297) 600 mg, 6-ftase EC 3.1.3.26 (4a27) 300 FTU, other additives: lactic acid (E-270), citric acid (E-330), and calcium lactate (E-327).

⁵ Nutrient composition values were estimated according to INRA tables (Sauvant et al., 2004).

⁶ Fatty acid composition values of the complete feed rations were estimated using INRA tables (Sauvant et al., 2004) and the information on the fat source products used in each diet.

mummies, and their individual weights were registered within 24 h after birth. In addition, litter size and individual piglet weight were also registered at 21 days of age and weaning. Therefore, litter and piglet weight, as well as average daily weight gain, were calculated from 24 h to 21 days of age or up to weaning. All litter parameters were calculated for the sows that finished the trial (17 and 19 for control and n-3 LCFA diet, respectively).

Colostrum samples from each Iberian sow were obtained within the first 12 h after the birth of the first piglet, and milk samples

were collected at weaning by directly milking all mammary glands. Samples from the different nipples of each sow were pooled, and aliquots for FA, oxylipin, Ig and cytokine analysis were stored at –80 °C until processing. Sampling tubes for oxylipin determination contained 0.005% butylated hydroxytoluene (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) as an antioxidant. All colostrum and milk samples collected for subsequent analysis were prepared as described in Llauradó-Calero et al. (2021). Colostrum could only be sampled from 21 sows (11 control and 10 n-3 LCFA) and milk from 18 sows

(10 control and 8 n-3 LCFA). In addition, it was not possible to obtain sufficient milk from two of the n-3 LCFA sows for FA determinations; only oxylipins and immune indicators were analysed.

Quantitative analysis of fatty acids

Fat was directly extracted from 3 g of previously defrosted colostrum and milk using 100 ml of chloroform (Fisher Scientific, NH, USA) and methanol (Fisher Scientific, NH, USA) solution (2:1) according to Folch et al. (1957). For the analysis of the FA profiles, FA methyl esters (FAMES) were prepared by acidic transesterification in the presence of sulphuric acid (5% sulphuric acid in methanol, according to Sandler and Karo (1992)). FAs were analysed using a 7820A gas chromatograph (GC) equipped with a flame ionisation detector (FID). Separation was carried out on a capillary column (0.25 mm × 0.25 µm × 60 m; HP88, Agilent Technologies, PA, USA), using a temperature gradient with an initial temperature of 140 °C that increased at a rate of 4 °C/min until reaching 230 °C, followed by another increase at a rate of 7 °C/min to 250 °C, where it remained for 10 min. Injector and detector temperatures were set at 250 °C. Injection was in split mode at a ratio of 70:1. The carrier gas was helium at a flow rate of 1 mL/min in constant flow mode. Internal standards C17:0 and C19:0 were not used due to their presence in the samples. Individual FAs were identified by comparing their retention times with those of standard FAME Mix C4–C24 (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA, USA). Results were expressed as mg of FA per g of extracted fat. The litter's milk intake was estimated by multiplying the litter's average daily gain from 24 h after birth until weaning by a factor of four, as suggested by the Gff (2006). EPA and DHA intakes from milk were calculated considering the litter's estimated milk intake and the EPA and DHA concentrations analysed in milk. EPA and DHA intakes from creep feed were estimated considering a creep feed disappearance of 270 g, as suggested by Muro et al. (2023), and the estimated EPA and DHA concentrations in the feed. EPA and DHA yields were calculated from the ratio between the litter's daily intake of the FA from milk and the sow's daily FA intake.

Quantitative analysis of oxylipins

Aliquots of 1 ml of colostrum and milk samples were treated according to Llauradó-Calero et al. (2021) to analyse oxylipin concentrations using an Ultra High-Performance Liquid Chromatography 1290 Series coupled to a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer 6490 series instrument (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) with an analytical column Eclipse XDB C18 1.8 µL (2.1 × 150 mm) (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA). Chromatographic separation was achieved through a gradient elution using LC-MS water (Scharlab, Barcelona, Spain) (0.01% acetic acid (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany)) and acetonitrile:methanol (85:15, v/v) as mobile phases at 45 °C and with a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. The injection volume of injection was 10 µL at 4 °C. The electrospray source ionisation was in negative mode, and the acquisition was performed using dynamic multiple reaction monitoring (MRM). Sixty-seven FA-derived oxylipins were identified using standard or tentative identification (for those oxylipins with no commercially available standard) and quantified as previously described in Llauradó-Calero et al. (2021). The standards used were ALA and GLA Oxylipin LC-MS Mixture, 10(s),17 (s)-DiHDHA (NDP1), (±)11(12)-DiHET, EPA Oxylipin LC-MS Mixture, 20-HETE, 8-iso Prostaglandin F2a, Leukotriene B4 Pathway LC-MS Mixture, Linoleic Acid Oxylipins LC-MS Mixture, Lipoxin LC-MS Mixture, Primary COX and LOX LC-MS Mixture, SPM D-series LC-MS Mixture, and SPM E-series LC-MS Mixture, and isotope labelled Arachidonic acid-d8, Deuterated Linoleic Acid Oxylipins LC-MS Mixture, Deuterated Primary COX and LOX LC-MS Mixture, 8-iso Prostaglandin F2a-d4, Leukotriene B4-d4, Lipoxin

A4-d5, and Resolvin D1-d5 (Cayman chemicals, Ann Arbor, MI, USA). Tentative identification considered published data about chromatographic behaviour on C18 columns, MS (Astarita et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2015; Ostermann, 2017), and available data regarding the main oxylipin in the studied matrices (Bruins et al., 2013; Mavangira et al., 2015).

Quantitative analysis of immune indicators

The concentrations of Ig (IgG, IgA, and IgM) and cytokines (IL1β, IL6, IL10, and TNF-α) as immune indicators in colostrum and milk were quantitatively measured following the manufacturer's protocols of different commercial sandwich ELISA kits, as previously described in Llauradó-Calero et al. (2021). The references of the ELISA kits used were Pig IgG ELISA Kit (E101-104; Bethyl Laboratories, Montgomery, Tx, USA), Pig IgA ELISA Kit (ab190536; Abcam, Cambridge, UK), Pig IgM ELISA Kit (ab190537; Abcam, Cambridge, UK), Pig IL-1β ELISA Kit (ab100754; Abcam, Cambridge, UK), Pig IL-6 ELISA Kit (ab100755; Abcam, Cambridge, UK), Swine IL-10 ELISA Kit (KSC0101; Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA), and Pig TNF-α ELISA Kit (ab100756; Abcam, Cambridge, UK). For all ELISA kits used, the intra- and inter-assay CV were < 10% and < 12%, respectively.

Statistical analysis

ANOVA was conducted with SAS software (SAS/STAT 14.1; SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC, USA) using the MIXED procedure for continuous variables and the GLIMMIX procedure for discrete variables, including dietary treatment as a fixed effect. BW and parity of the sows at the beginning of the trial were initially introduced as covariates in the model. However, only BW was used as a covariate for statistical analysis since no effect of sow parity was observed. "Days of lactation" was used as a covariable for all data at weaning.

The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test was applied to the numbers of stillborn piglets, mummies, and deaths during lactation, and a logarithmic transformation ($\log_{10}(X + 1)$) was performed to normalise the oxylipin concentration data. However, original data are presented in the tables. When the limit of detection was not reached, values were replaced by 1/5 of the minimum positive value of each variable. The Smirnov-Grubbs test was used to test data for outliers; values were excluded if $P < 0.01$ (Grubbs, 1969). All results are expressed as least squares means ± RMSE, except oxylipins, which are expressed as means ± RMSE. P -values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant differences, while those at $P < 0.1$ are reported as tendencies.

Correlation analysis was performed only between FAs or oxylipins and immune indicators in colostrum or milk that were differentially expressed between dietary treatments. The Pearson correlation coefficient was obtained using SAS software through the PROC CORR procedure. A significant correlation level was set at $P < 0.05$. Principal Component Analysis of FAs and oxylipins and the oxylipin heatmap were performed using MetaboAnalyst 5.0 (<https://www.metaboanalyst.ca>, Alberta, CA, USA).

Results

Sow fertility and BW

After the mating period, thirty-six sows became pregnant (90% fertility), of which 17 were in the control group and 19 were in the n-3 LCFA group. The sows' BW at mating (115.3 kg; RMSE: 24.0), upon entering the farrowing unit (148.1 kg; RMSE: 26.7), and at weaning (139.8 kg; RMSE: 26.8) did not differ between treatment groups ($P > 0.521$). Likewise, average daily weight changes during gestation (0.300 kg; RMSE: 0.09), lactation (−0.298 kg; RMSE:

0.29), or the whole trial (0.150 kg; RMSE: 0.07) did not differ between dietary treatments ($P > 0.564$). Sows' average daily feed intake during lactation was also similar between treatments (3.83 kg; $P = 0.192$). Considering their average feed intake, it was estimated that sows from the n-3 LCFA group had a daily intake of 4.71 g of EPA and 3.81 g of DHA.

In reference to backfat measurements at mating (2.73 cm interscapular and 1.52 cm sacral backfat; RMSE: 1.35 for and 0.75, respectively), at entering the farrowing unit (3.19 cm interscapular and 1.72 cm sacral backfat; RMSE: 1.46 for and 0.66, respectively), and at weaning (3.27 cm interscapular and 1.99 cm sacral backfat; RMSE: 1.65 and 0.69, respectively), no changes were observed due to the inclusion of dietary fish oil ($P > 0.416$).

Litter traits and piglet growth

Litter characteristics at 24 h after birth, 21 days of age, and weaning are presented in Table 2. No differences were observed between treatments for the total number of piglets born, live-born or stillborn ($P > 0.765$), and no mummies were found. The number of piglets at 21 days and weaning was also similar between groups ($P > 0.660$), as was the number of dead piglets per litter during lactation ($P = 0.606$). No treatment effects were observed for litter weight at 24 h, day 21, or weaning. In contrast, individual piglet BW at 24 h was greater in the control than in the n-3 LCFA group ($P = 0.005$), whereas individual piglet BW at weaning and piglet average daily gain between 24 h after birth and weaning were greater ($P = 0.017$ and $P = 0.007$, respectively) in the n-3 LCFA than in the control group.

Fatty acid profile

The effects of n-3 LCFA inclusion in the sows' diet on the fat content and FA composition of colostrum and milk are shown in Table 3. The fat content in colostrum and milk did not differ between dietary treatments. In colostrum, total saturated FAs were similar between groups ($P = 0.325$). However, margaric acid (C17:0) tended to be higher ($P = 0.054$), and tricosylic acid (C23:0) was higher ($P < 0.001$) in n-3 LCFA-fed sows. In contrast, total monounsaturated and polyunsaturated FAs were lower ($P = 0.001$) and higher ($P = 0.019$), respectively, in n-3 LCFA-fed sows. In terms of individual FAs, monounsaturated oleic acid (C18:1 n-9 *cis*) ($P < 0.001$), elaidic or trans-oleic acid (C18:1 n-9 *trans*) ($P = 0.010$), and the polyunsaturated FA arachidonic acid (C20:4 n-6) ($P = 0.013$) were lower in the colostrum of sows that were fed with the fish oil-rich diet. Conversely, EPA (C20:5 n-3) ($P < 0.001$), docosapentaenoic acid (C22:5 n-3) ($P < 0.001$), and DHA (C22:6 n-3) ($P < 0.001$) were higher in n-3 LCFA-fed sows. Consequently, n-3 FAs were also higher ($P < 0.001$), and the n-6:n-3 ratio was significantly lower ($P < 0.001$) in sows fed the n-3 LCFA-rich diet.

As for milk, the total amount of saturated FAs was higher in n-3 LCFA-fed sows ($P < 0.001$), the total amount of monounsaturated FAs was lower ($P = 0.005$), and the total amount of polyunsaturated FAs did not differ between dietary treatments ($P = 0.308$). The higher proportion of saturated FAs was mainly due to higher concentrations of myristic acid (C14:0) ($P = 0.039$), palmitic acid (C16:0) ($P = 0.001$), and margaric acid (C17:0) ($P = 0.007$); the lower amount of monounsaturated FAs was mainly because of the lower concentrations of oleic acid (C18:1 n-9 *cis*) ($P = 0.010$) and elaidic or trans-oleic acid (C18:1 n-9 *trans*) ($P < 0.001$). In terms of polyunsaturated FAs, no differences were observed in their total amount; however, the concentrations of α -linolenic acid (C18:3 n-3 *cis*) ($P = 0.075$), arachidonic acid (C20:4 n-6) ($P = 0.083$), EPA (C20:5 n-3) ($P < 0.001$), docosapentaenoic acid (C22:5 n-3) ($P = 0.005$), and DHA (C22:6 n-3) ($P < 0.001$) were higher or tended

to be higher in milk from n-3 LCFA-fed sows, while dihomogamma-linolenic acid (C20:3 n-6) tended to be lower ($P = 0.056$). Like colostrum, the total amount of n-3 FA in milk was also higher ($P < 0.001$) due to dietary fish oil, which led to a lower n-6:n-3 ratio ($P < 0.001$). The Principal Component Analysis (Fig. 1, A) revealed different distributions of the samples according to sample type (colostrum or milk) and diet (control or n-3 LCFA). DHA, EPA, and arachidonic acid were the FAs with the highest contribution to explaining the separation between treatments in the principal component analysis distribution.

Oxylipin profile

The results of the oxylipin analysis are shown in detail in Supplementary Table S1 and Supplementary Table S2 for colostrum and milk, respectively. In colostrum, a total of 32 oxylipins were higher ($P < 0.05$) and one tended to be lower ($P < 0.01$) in the n-3 LCFA group in comparison with the control group. The EPA-derived oxylipins that were higher in the fish oil-fed sows were mainly hydroxyl-EPA metabolites, such as 5(s)-, 8-, 9-, 11-, 12(s)-, 15(s)-, and 18-hydroxy-EPA ($P < 0.001$ for all oxylipins), and 17,18-dihydroxy-eicosatetraenoic acid ($P < 0.001$). In terms of DHA-derived oxylipins, higher concentrations of hydroxyl-DHA metabolites, such as 4-, 7-, 8-, 10-, 11-, 13-, 14-, 16-, 17-, and 20-hydroxy-DHA (all $P < 0.001$), and 10(s),17(s)-dihydroxy-DHA (also known as Neuroprotectin D1; $P = 0.002$) were observed in the colostrum of n-3 LCFA-fed sows. Other DHA-derived oxylipins, such as 7,8-, 10,11-, 13,14-, 16,17-, and 19,20-dihydroxy-docosapentaenoic acid ($P < 0.01$) and Resolvin D5 ($P < 0.001$) were also higher in sows fed n-3 LCFA. Some oxylipins derived from n-6 LCFA were also modified by the inclusion of fish oil. Specifically, 12,13- and 15,16-dihydroxy-octadecadienoic acid ($P = 0.021$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively), 12(13)-dihydroxy-octadecenoic acid ($P = 0.019$), 12(13)-epoxy-octadecenoic acid ($P = 0.049$) and 9-oxo-octadecadienoic acid ($P = 0.030$) derived from linoleic acid, and 5,6- and 14,15-dihydroxy-eicosatrienoic acid ($P = 0.016$ and $P = 0.008$, respectively) derived from arachidonic acid, were also higher in the colostrum of n-3 LCFA-fed sows; 8,9-epoxy-eicosatrienoic acid ($P = 0.088$) (also derived from arachidonic acid) tended to be lower.

The concentration of 25 oxylipins was higher, and one tended to be higher, while two were lower and three tended to be lower in milk from sows fed the n-3 LCFA diet in comparison with milk from control sows. Among these, the EPA-derived oxylipins that were higher were hydroxyl-EPA metabolites, such as 5(s)-, 8-, 9-, 11-, 12(s)-, 15(s)-, and 18-hydroxy-EPA (all $P < 0.01$, except 12(s)-hydroxy-EPA ($P = 0.005$)), and also 11,12- and 17,18-dihydroxy-eicosatetraenoic acid ($P = 0.087$ and $P < 0.001$, respectively). The DHA-derived oxylipins that were higher were 4-, 7-, 8-, 10-, 11-, 13-, 14-, 16-, 17-, and 20-hydroxy-DHA ($P < 0.05$), 10(s),17(s)-dihydroxy-docosahexaenoic acid, and 7,8-, 10,11-, 13,14-, 16,17-, and 19,20-dihydroxy-docosapentaenoic acid (all $P < 0.001$), and Resolvin D5 ($P < 0.001$). In addition to the changes in EPA- and DHA-derived oxylipins, 9(10)-dihydroxy-octadecenoic acid ($P = 0.027$) derived from linoleic acid and thromboxane B2 ($P = 0.057$), 11(12)-dihydroxy-eicosatrienoic acid ($P = 0.064$), 20-hydroxy-eicosatetraenoic acid ($P = 0.054$), and 11,12-epoxy-eicosatrienoic acid ($P = 0.029$) derived from arachidonic acid were lower or tended to be lower in milk from n-3 LCFA-fed sows.

Principal Component Analysis revealed a distinctly different distribution of samples in 2D plots according to sample type (colostrum or milk) and diet (control or n-3 LCFA) (Fig. 1, B). However, no single change in any particular oxylipin stands out; rather, it is the global oxylipin profile that causes the different distribution according to dietary treatment and sample type. The heatmap presented in Fig. 2 shows how, for both colostrum and milk, the

Table 2
Effect of fish oil in the diet of Iberian sows during gestation and lactation on litter characteristics and the growth performance of suckling piglets¹.

Item	Control (n = 17)	n-3 LCFA (n = 19)	RMSE	P-value
At 24 h after birth				
Average litter size (total born)	8.64	8.65	2.15	0.898
Live-born piglets	7.38	7.33	2.44	0.822
Stillborn piglets	1.26	1.32	1.49	0.765
Average litter weight (kg)	10.9	10.2	2.28	0.350
Average live litter weight (kg)	9.73	8.93	2.79	0.420
Average piglet BW (kg)	1.27	1.18	0.29	0.006
Average live piglet BW (kg)	1.32	1.22	0.27	0.005
At 21 days of age				
Average litter size (piglets)	6.27	6.04	1.95	0.728
Average litter weight (kg)	28.5	27.7	7.38	0.744
Litter ADG (24 h → 21 d) (kg)	0.894	0.892	0.27	0.987
Average piglet BW (kg)	4.56	4.61	1.05	0.725
Piglet ADG (24 h → 21 d) (kg)	0.152	0.159	0.04	0.305
At weaning				
Average weaning age (days)	30.7	31.0	2.04	0.295
Average litter size (piglets)	6.28	5.97	1.96	0.660
Average lactation mortality (piglets)	1.10	1.35	1.41	0.606
Average litter weight (kg)	34.9	36.6	9.59	0.641
Litter ADG (24 h → W) (kg)	0.815	0.887	0.26	0.434
Average piglet BW (kg)	5.52	6.05	1.59	0.017
Piglet ADG (24 h → W) (kg)	0.136	0.154	0.05	0.007

Abbreviations: ADG = average daily gain; LCFA = long-chain fatty acid; W = weaning.

¹ Values are least squares means ± RMSE.**Table 3**
Effect of fish oil in the diet of Iberian sows during gestation and lactation on colostrum (obtained during the first 12 h after farrowing) and milk (at weaning): fatty acid profile¹.

Item	Colostrum				Milk			
	Control (n = 10)	n-3 LCFA (n = 11)	RMSE	P-value	Control (n = 10)	n-3 LCFA (n = 6)	RMSE	P-value
Fat (g/kg sample)	58.8	56.9	3.92	0.176	56.8	59.0	4.06	0.326
Fatty acid (mg FA/g fat)								
C14:0	18.5	19.0	2.75	0.672	22.4	26.6	3.57	0.039
C16:0	180	183	11.7	0.575	209	242	15.7	0.001
C16:1	54.2	48.3	12.1	0.297	85.6	91.7	21.0	0.586
C17:0	3.45	4.08	0.68	0.054	1.91	3.22	0.79	0.007
C18:0	41.1	42.7	6.30	0.576	33.9	39.3	6.80	0.144
C18:1 n-9 <i>cis</i>	247	212	19.0	<0.001	236	201	22.7	0.010
C18:1 n-9 <i>trans</i>	1.80	1.13	0.52	0.010	1.69	0.73	0.40	<0.001
C18:2 n-6 <i>cis</i>	150	161	21.6	0.294	115	113	20.2	0.834
C18:3 n-3 <i>cis</i>	9.78	11.5	3.45	0.281	6.66	7.63	0.98	0.075
C20:3 n-6	3.44	3.91	2.21	0.645	8.03	3.35	4.35	0.056
C20:4 n-6	10.2	5.77	3.59	0.013	1.14	2.30	1.20	0.083
C20:5 n-3	1.23	7.84	1.86	<0.001	1.35	7.15	1.19	<0.001
C22:5 n-3	2.50	6.89	1.56	<0.001	2.07	4.23	1.23	0.005
C22:6 n-3	1.55	13.6	3.66	<0.001	1.38	11.1	1.35	<0.001
C23:0	0.45	1.50	0.59	<0.001	1.21	0.83	1.04	0.483
Minor FA ²	14.7	16.3	3.19	0.283	18.4	17.7	2.99	0.664
SFA	248	255	16.2	0.325	276	318	17.1	<0.001
MUFA	310	268	21.4	0.001	333	303	17.1	0.005
PUFA	182	214	27.4	0.019	137	151	24.3	0.308
n-3	15.1	39.8	8.30	<0.001	11.5	30.1	3.20	<0.001
n-6	170	178	22.7	0.496	128	123	23.3	0.682
n-6:n-3	11.5	4.94	1.85	<0.001	11.2	4.13	1.20	<0.001

Abbreviations: FA = fatty acid; LCFA = long-chain fatty acid; MUFA = monounsaturated fatty acid; PUFA = polyunsaturated fatty acid; SFA = saturated fatty acid.

¹ FA quantification results are reported from C12:0. Values are least squares means ± RMSE.² Minor FAs include C12:0, C14:1 n-9 *cis*, C15:0, C17:1, C20:1 n-9 *cis*, C21:0, and C24:0.

oxylipins derived from EPA and DHA were highly increased by dietary fish oil. It can also be observed that the concentration of most oxylipins is higher in milk. [Supplementary Fig. S1](#) represents a schematic global overview of all oxylipins that were modified by treatment, including their FA precursor and synthesis pathway.

Immunological analysis

The concentrations of Ig and cytokines in colostrum and milk from sows that were fed with the control or n-3 LCFA diets are reported in [Table 4](#). In colostrum, IgG and IgA concentrations were

Fig. 1. Principal component analysis two-dimension score plot showing the influence of fish oil in the diet of Iberian sows during gestation and lactation on the fatty acid (A) and oxylipin (B) profiles of colostrum (obtained during the first 12 h after farrowing) and milk (at weaning). Values are means of 10 control and 11 n-3 LCFA colostrum samples for both FA and oxylipin analyses, 10 control and 6 n-3 LCFA milk samples, and 10 control and 8 n-3 LCFA milk samples for FA and oxylipin analyses, respectively. Abbreviations: LCFA = long-chain fatty acid; PC = principal component.

higher in the n-3 LCFA than in the control group ($P = 0.025$ and $P = 0.026$, respectively). However, no influence of dietary n-3 LCFAs was observed in the concentrations of Ig in milk. No differences between dietary treatments for any of the cytokines tested were observed in colostrum or milk.

Correlations between fatty acids or oxylipins and immune indicators modified by fish oil

The analyses of correlations between FAs or oxylipins and immune indicators were only performed for colostrum, as no statistical differences between treatments were observed for immune indicators in milk. The correlations established between modified FAs or oxylipins and IgG and IgA are schematically shown in Fig. 3 A and B, respectively. The IgA concentration in colostrum was positively correlated with EPA ($r = 0.50$, $P = 0.022$), docosapentaenoic acid ($r = 0.49$, $P = 0.023$), and DHA ($r = 0.52$, $P = 0.016$), and negatively correlated with oleic acid ($r = -0.51$, $P = 0.018$). However, no correlations between IgG and the different FAs were observed. In reference to oxylipins, the IgG concentration in colostrum was correlated with linoleic acid-derived oxylipins 12,13-dihydroxy-octadecadienoic acid, 12(13)-dihydroxy-octadecenoic acid, 12(13)-epoxy-octadecenoic acid, and 9-oxo-octadecadienoic acid (all $r \geq 0.49$, $P \leq 0.046$); the arachidonic acid-derived oxylipin 14,15-dihydroxy-eicosatrienoic acid ($r = 0.49$, $P = 0.047$); the EPA-derived oxylipin 8-hydroxy-EPA ($r = 0.53$, $P = 0.028$); and DHA-derived oxylipins 13-, 16-, and 20-hydroxy-DHA and 13,14-, 16,17-, and 19,20- dihydroxy-docosapentaenoic acid (all $r \geq 0.48$, $P \leq 0.049$). On the other hand, IgA was correlated with linoleic acid-derived oxylipins 12,13- and 15,16-dihydroxy-octadecadienoic acid, 12(13)-epoxy-octadecenoic acid, and 9-oxo-octadecadienoic acid (all $r \geq 0.46$, $P \leq 0.040$); the arachidonic acid-derived oxylipin 14,15-dihydroxy-eicosatrienoic acid ($r = 0.51$, $P = 0.021$); EPA-derived oxylipins 8-, 9-, 12(s)-, 15(s)-, and 18-hydroxy-EPA and 17,18-dihydroxy-eicosatetraenoic acid (all $r \geq 0.45$, $P \leq 0.048$); and DHA-derived oxylipins 7-, 8-, 10-,

11-, 13-, 16-, 17-, and 20-hydroxy-DHA, Resolvin D5, and 10,11-, 13,14-, 16,17-, and 19,20- dihydroxy-docosapentaenoic acid (all $r \geq 0.47$, $P \leq 0.038$).

Discussion

Autochthonous pig breeds are usually less productive than their conventional counterparts. Notably, the Iberian pig is generally characterised by low fertility and growth rates, resulting in a low number of weaned piglets per sow, with low BW and higher within-litter BW variation at weaning (IRTA, 2023). Therefore, it is of interest to develop perinatal nutritional strategies or improve farm management to increase piglet growth and survival during lactation. For this purpose, fish oil was added to sow and creep feed diets, and this was tested in the current study. Previous studies in conventional breeds reported a reduction in litter size when the sows were fed with salmon oil from day 60 of gestation (Rooke et al., 2001a) or a numerical decrease in the total number of piglets born when fed fish oil during the whole gestation (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021). However, in the present study, no significant differences in litter size were observed between dietary treatments when fish oil was included in sows' diets from mating. Herein, we observed that feeding sows with n-3 LCFAs reduced the BW of piglets measured 24 h after birth, which aligns with previous results in conventional breeds (Rooke et al., 2001b; Laws et al., 2007). One possible explanation for this result may be the reduced availability of arachidonic acid (necessary for embryonic development in piglets (Fainberg et al., 2014)) in the n-3 LCFA group compared with control piglets. A lower concentration of this FA in blood at the end of gestation was previously reported in conventional breeds of sows fed fish oil diets (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2022). In contrast, in the current study, piglets from the n-3 LCFA group were significantly heavier at weaning and had a higher average daily gain during the entire lactation period than those from the control group. This fact could be an indication of compensatory growth in n-3 LCFA piglets during lactation (Hawe et al., 2020). In

Fig. 2. Fish oil in the diet of Iberian sows during gestation and lactation increased eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA) and docosahexaenoic acid (DHA)-derived oxylipins in both colostrum (obtained during the first 12 h after farrowing) and milk (at weaning). Values are means of 10 control and 11 n-3 LCFA colostrum samples and 10 control and 8 n-3 LCFA milk samples. Abbreviations: AA = arachidonic acid; ALA = α -linolenic acid; DiHDHA = dihydroxy-docosahexaenoic acid; DiHDPE = dihydroxy-docosapentaenoic acid; DiHETE = dihydroxy-eicosatetraenoic acid; DiHODE = dihydroxy-octadecadienoic acid; DiHOME = dihydroxy-octadecenoic acid; DHET = dihydroxy-eicosatrienoic acid; EET = epoxy-eicosatrienoic acid; EpOME = epoxy-octadecenoic acid; HDHA = hydroxy-docosahexaenoic acid; HEPE = hydroxy-eicosapentaenoic acid; HETE = hydroxy-eicosatetraenoic acid; HHTrE = hydroxy-heptadecatrienoic acid; HODE = hydroxy-octadecadienoic acid; HOTrE = hydroxy-octadecatrienoic acid; LA = linoleic acid; LCFA = long-chain fatty acid; LT = leukotriene; OxoETE = oxo-eicosatetraenoic acid; OxoODE = oxo-octadecadienoic acid; PG = prostaglandin; Rv = resolvin; TriHETrE = trihydroxy-eicosatrienoic acid; TriHOME = trihydroxy-octadecenoic acid; TX = thromboxane.

conventional breeds, Llauradó-Calero et al. (2021) also observed that fish oil tended to increase piglet weight gain during lactation and BW at weaning; however, although not significant, the litter size from those sows was also smaller. Therefore, they could not conclude whether the increased BW was due to the dietary fish

oil or easier access of the piglets to colostrum and milk. In the present study, the increased piglet growth during lactation can be assigned to the dietary n-3 LCFA as no differences in litter size were observed. A recent meta-analysis comprising 20 studies indicated that the average daily litter creep feed disappearance in con-

Table 4
Effect of fish oil in the diet of Iberian sows during gestation and lactation on colostrum (obtained during the first 12 h after farrowing) and milk (at weaning) immune indicators¹.

Item	Colostrum				Milk			
	Control (n = 10)	n-3 LCFA (n = 11)	RMSE	P-value	Control (n = 10)	n-3 LCFA (n = 8)	RMSE	P-value
Immunoglobulins (mg/mL)								
IgG	30.1	50.7	17.7	0.025	0.73	0.88	0.53	0.555
IgA	6.64	12.4	5.45	0.026	2.32	3.13	1.42	0.243
IgM	3.09	4.13	1.57	0.147	0.76	0.82	0.22	0.590
Cytokines (ng/mL)								
IL-1β	10.3	10.4	9.51	0.978	1.12	1.02	1.87	0.913
IL-6	36.6	111	145	0.252	1.52	1.27	2.56	0.856
IL-10	0.72	1.42	2.18	0.466	0.09	0.08	0.05	0.903
TNF-α	0.14	0.06	0.28	0.526	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.307

Abbreviations: IgA = immunoglobulin A; IgG = immunoglobulin G; IgM = immunoglobulin M; IL-1β = interleukin 1β; IL-6 = interleukin 6; IL-10 = interleukin 10; LCFA = long-chain fatty acid; TNF-α = tumour necrosis factor-α.

Fig. 3. Correlations between fatty acids and immunoglobulins (A) and between oxylipins and immunoglobulins (B) modified by fish oil in the diet of Iberian sows during gestation and lactation in colostrum (obtained during the first 12 h after farrowing). Positive correlations are represented by the Pearson correlation coefficient (r) in green, while negative correlations are shown in red. A significant correlation level was set at $P < 0.05$. Boxes containing fatty acids and their derived oxylipins are the same colour (oleic acid, orange; linoleic acid-derived oxylipins, brown; arachidonic acid-derived oxylipin, cream; eicosapentaenoic acid and its derived oxylipins, blue; docosapentaenoic acid, light orange; docosahexaenoic acid and its derived oxylipins, light red). Abbreviations: DHA = docosahexaenoic acid; DHET = dihydroxy-eicosatrienoic acid; DiHDPE = dihydroxy-docosapentaenoic acid; DiHETE = dihydroxy-eicosatetraenoic acid; DiHODE = dihydroxy-octadecadienoic acid; DiHOME = dihydroxy-octadecenoic acid; DPA = docosapentaenoic acid; EPA = eicosapentaenoic acid; EpOME = epoxy-octadecenoic acid; HDHA = hydroxy-docosahexaenoic acid; HDHA = hydroxy-docosahexaenoic acid; HEPE = hydroxy-eicosapentaenoic acid; IgA = immunoglobulin A; IgG = immunoglobulin G; OA = oleic acid; OxoODE = oxo-octadecadienoic acid; Rv = resolvin.

ventional breeds is ca. 270 g (Muro et al., 2023). Creep feed is mainly offered to piglets to adapt animals to the solid feed that will be provided after weaning. However, during this period, in most cases, piglets are not really eating but rather playing with feed. In the current study, the daily estimated ingesta of EPA and DHA via milk per litter is 1 497 and 2 324 mg, respectively, while via creep feed, it is just 331 and 267 mg, respectively. This suggests that the impact of n-3 LCFA on suckling piglet performance could be mainly attributed to the n-3 LCFA intake from milk.

Colostrum and milk are the first sources of nutrients and play a crucial role in the proper development of newborn piglets. Moreover, piglets have a high capacity to digest the lipids present in colostrum and milk (Azain, 2001), which makes these nutrient sources suitable feeds for the mother-offspring transference of FAs (Lauridsen, 2020). In the present study, the inclusion of fish oil in sow diets mainly increased the total amount of n-3 FAs due to the increased concentration of EPA, docosapentaenoic acid, and DHA in both colostrum and milk, decreasing the n-6:n-3 ratio. These effects align with those observed in colostrum and milk from conventional breeds (Rooke et al., 2001b; Eastwood et al., 2014; Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021). From the current results, EPA has an estimated yield of 32% and DHA 61% in milk. These yields are similar to those from conventional breeds (Llauradó-Calero et al.,

2021). A higher oxidation of EPA may explain the difference between the EPA and DHA yields. EPA-derived oxylipins in milk were ca. 99 500 pg/mL, while those derived from DHA were ca. 44 000 pg/mL. In addition, as previously observed in conventional breeds (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021), the concentration of arachidonic acid in colostrum from Iberian sows was also decreased. However, this reduction was not observed in milk in the current study. The reduction of long-chain n-6 FA by the dietary inclusion of fish oil rich in n-3 FA could be explained by the competition between the n-3 and n-6 FA families at the level of desaturation and chain elongation as both pathways are regulated by the same rate-limiting enzymes (Vance and Vance, 1991). Dietary fish oil increased total polyunsaturated FAs in the colostrum of Iberian (this study) and conventional (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021) breeds; however, an increase in total saturated FAs in milk and a reduction in total monounsaturated FAs in colostrum and milk were only observed in Iberian sows. Along this line, the principal component analysis represented in Supplementary Fig. S2(A and B) shows that the FA profiles were clearly differentiated between breeds. These differences in the FA profile could be explained because conventional breeds were selected to be lean, while autochthonous breeds are more prone to synthesise *de novo* FAs and, therefore, accumulate much more saturated FAs.

Polyunsaturated FAs are oxidised via enzymatic or non-enzymatic oxygen-dependent reactions. The products of these oxidation reactions are commonly known as oxylipins and are considered the main mediators of the effects of polyunsaturated FAs in the body (Gabbs et al., 2015). Current nutritional research associates n-6 FAs and their derivative oxylipins with pro-inflammatory activities (Gabbs et al., 2015), while n-3 FAs and their oxygenated derivatives are associated with anti-inflammatory and inflammation-resolving roles (Calder, 2010). In this study, the inclusion of fish oil in sow diets largely increased oxygenated EPA and DHA derivatives in both colostrum and milk. Considering that specific roles have not been described yet for all oxylipins, EPA derivatives 12(s)-, 15(s)-, and 18-hydroxy-EPA, and DHA derivatives 13- and 17-hydroxy-DHA, 10(s), 17(s)-dihydroxy-DHA (neuroprotectin D1) and resolvin D5 stand out. Certain anti-inflammatory activities have been described for these prominent oxylipins, mainly in cell culture and animal models. The hydroxy-EPA or -DHA derivatives are formed via the lipoxygenase enzymatic pathway (Astarita et al., 2015; Gabbs et al., 2015). Within them, 12(s)-hydroxy-EPA is related to platelet-neutrophil interaction (von Schacky et al., 1990), 15(s)-hydroxy-EPA with the resolution phase of inflammation (Miller et al., 1990), and 18-hydroxy-EPA, 13-hydroxy-DHA, and 17-hydroxy-DHA with the reduction or inhibition of some pro-inflammatory cytokine production (Gabbs et al., 2015). Neuroprotectin D1 and resolvin D5 are final mediators also formed through the enzymatic pathway involving the lipoxygenase pathway (Astarita et al., 2015; Gabbs et al., 2015). Specifically, neuroprotectin D1 is associated with an anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective role (Bazan, 2005), and resolvin D5 possesses inflammation-resolving activity through its ability to reduce the production of pro-inflammatory cytokines (Chiang et al., 2012) and may protect against some bacterial infections (Cardoso et al., 2023). On the other hand, it should be mentioned that changes in the concentration of oxylipins derived from other FAs were also detected. The most notable difference between dietary treatments was the increase in 12(13)-dihydroxy-octadecenoic acid in the colostrum of n-3 LCFA-fed sows. This oxylipin is a derivative of linoleic acid formed via cytochrome P450 (Astarita et al., 2015; Gabbs et al., 2015), which was recently proposed to act as a mechanism to activate FA-transporter translocation in brown adipocytes, increasing FA uptake and improving thermogenesis (a critical physiological process for piglets during the early stages of life) by providing fuel (Lynes et al., 2017). As for FA composition, specific oxylipin changes due to dietary treatment were similar between conventional and Iberian sows; however, the oxylipin profile of both colostrum and milk is clearly differentiated between breeds, as shown in the principal component analyses represented in Supplementary Fig. S2 (C and D).

The immune molecules of colostrum and milk are also of great importance since piglets are born without a developed immune system (Le Dividich et al., 2005). For this reason, the effects of changing the profiles of FAs and their oxygenated derivatives on the immune parameters is a matter of interest (Mitre et al., 2005; Leonard et al., 2010; Yao et al., 2012; Luo et al., 2020). In terms of Igs, Mitre et al. (2005) reported increases in colostrum and milk IgG after feeding sows a diet supplemented with 32 g/day shark-liver oil from 5 weeks before parturition until weaning. Leonard et al. (2010) observed no changes with a dietary inclusion of 100 g/day of fish oil from day 109 of gestation until weaning. Furthermore, Yao et al. (2012) described higher concentrations of IgG in colostrum and IgM in milk when sows were fed diets with a 9:1 n-6:n-3 ratio from day 108 of gestation until weaning compared with sows that were fed a 3:1 n-6:n-3 ratio. In the current study, dietary n-3 LCFAs increased IgG in colostrum but did not affect Igs in milk. The increased colostrum IgG concentration was also described by Luo et al. (2020). However, in the previous study, fish oil was only provided from ca. day 80 of gestation.

Moreover, in the current study, IgA was also increased in colostrum by dietary n-3 LCFAs, which was not observed in any of the aforementioned studies. In contrast to our previous study with conventional sows, which found no effect of dietary n-3 LCFAs on the concentration of any particular Ig in colostrum and milk (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021), in this study with Iberian sows, the observed effects could imply an improvement in the quality of the colostrum and consequently the maternal transference of passive immunity. Despite the low correlation coefficients, colostrum IgA concentration was negatively correlated with oleic acid and positively correlated with n-3 FAs, suggesting FA regulation in the secretion of IgA. Indeed, colostrum IgA concentration is correlated with almost all increased oxylipins derived from linoleic acid, arachidonic acid, EPA, and DHA. Therefore, we could not discriminate whether regulation was from FA oxidation via the CYP or LOX pathways. Colostral IgG did not correlate with any FA but did correlate with oxylipins derived from linoleic acid, arachidonic, EPA, and DHA. As a difference, linoleic acid-derived 12(13)-dihydroxy-octadecenoic acid was only correlated with colostrum IgG concentration. A recent publication underlies that the mechanism through which n-6 and n-3 PUFAs alter Ig concentrations is not yet understood (Reis et al., 2024), highlighting the need for further studies to elucidate the impacts of n-3 LCFA on immune parameters. On the other hand, in the current study, no influence of the dietary inclusion of n-3 LCFAs was observed on the concentration of the analysed cytokines, which contrasts with previous studies with conventional sows that reported a decreased concentration of the pro-inflammatory cytokine TNF- α in milk (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021; Luo et al., 2020). In this way, the results reported in the literature, along with the results obtained in both this trial and that conducted on conventional sows, indicate that dietary n-3 LCFAs clearly influence colostrum and milk composition. However, in terms of immune indicators, the n-3 LCFA source used, the inclusion level and duration, as well as the genetics of the sow, are factors to be considered and may explain the variability in the results described within different studies.

Therefore, the present study contributes to our knowledge of the oxygenated-lipid mediators of dietary n-3 LCFAs on colostrum and milk composition in Iberian sows. In addition, testing the impact of inclusion with this type of fat in a low-productivity autochthonous breed complements the knowledge generated by previous studies on conventional sows. To conclude, the inclusion of fish oil in Iberian sow diets increased piglet weight gain during lactation and BW at weaning, as well as the levels of EPA, DHA, and their derivative oxylipins in colostrum and milk, and IgG and IgA levels in colostrum. Consequently, due to the anti-inflammatory and inflammation-resolving activity associated with n-3 FA-derived oxylipins and the role of colostrum and milk in the transference of passive maternal immunity, the results obtained could imply that dietary n-3 LCFAs improve the quality of colostrum and milk, and this may be key during the early life of Iberian piglets. Further studies are needed to understand the mode of action by which n-3 LCFAs and their derived oxylipins modulate cytokine and, in particular, Ig production.

Supplementary material

Supplementary Material for this article (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.animal.2025.101430>) can be found at the foot of the online page, in the Appendix section.

Ethics approval

The use of animals for this experiment was approved by IRTA's Ethics Committee on Animal Experimentation in accordance with

Directive 2010/63/EU of 22 September 2010 and according to the recommendation of the European Commission 2007/526/CE, the Spanish guidelines for the care and use of animals in research (B. O.E. number 34, Real Decreto 53/2013), and regional regulations on the use and handling of experimental animals (project number: 10294).

Data and model availability statement

None of the data were deposited in an official repository. The data that support the study findings are available from the authors upon request.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) did not use any AI and AI-assisted technologies.

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Declaration of interest

The Authors report no conflicts of interest.

Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge the research support services of the Facility of Innovation and Analysis in Animal Source Foodstuffs (SiPA) of SAIUEx from the Universidad de Extremadura for their technical assistance in the quantitative determination of fatty acid composition, the Metabolomics Facility of the Centre for Omic

Science (COS) Joint Unit of the Universitat Rovira i Virgili – Eurecat for their contribution to the metabolomic analysis of oxylipins, and the laboratory staff of IRTA-CRESA for their work related to the immune indicators study. Similar research has been published in commercial breeds (Llauradó-Calero et al., 2021) as well as part of the first author's PhD thesis (Llauradó-Calero, 2023).

Financial support statement

This research was supported by the National Institute for Agricultural and Food Research and Technology (INIA), through project RTA2017-00086-C02-02, and the Junta of Extremadura. E. Llauradó-Calero obtained an INIA grant (PRE2018-086726) to conduct the current research.

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